

PROBLEMS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL RESPONSIBILITY THROUGH DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCIES

Batirova Odinakhon

Andijan state pedagogical institute,
2nd year master's student in Pedagogy

Tel: +998880659808

odinaxonborirova98@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787955>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th November 2025

Accepted: 29th November 2025

Online: 30th November 2025

KEYWORDS

Pedagogical competence, professional responsibility, reflexive practice, pedagogical skills, advanced training, interactive methods, competency model, pedagogical monitoring, pedagogical personality.

ABSTRACT

This scientific article is devoted to the analysis of the role and importance of development of pedagogical competencies in formation of professional responsibility in teachers. In the educational process, the professional activity of a teacher is inextricably linked with his qualifications, pedagogical skills, communicative skills and personal qualities, and the low level of competencies directly affects the quality of education. Therefore, the development of professional competencies of teachers is one of the urgent tasks of the current education system. The components of pedagogical competence, the mechanisms of their development, the formation of competence as universal skills and how they affect the strengthening of professional responsibility are scientifically covered.

Introduction

In today's global educational environment, the development of pedagogical competencies is considered one of the most important factors in the formation of teachers' professional responsibility. In an era of widespread use of digital technologies and rapid modernization of the educational process, a teacher is required not only to have a deep knowledge of his subject, but also to master communicative, psychological, technological, methodological and social competencies. The quality of education depends on the effectiveness of the pedagogical activity, which in turn depends on the competence of the teacher. The professional responsibility of a teacher means his devotion to his profession, responsibility in fulfilling his teaching duties, and a deep understanding of responsibility for the fate of students.

From this point of view, the state educational policy, higher education institutions, the system of advanced training and the teacher's work on himself play an important role in the formation of teacher competence. If competencies are not properly developed, the quality of the educational process decreases, motivation among students decreases, methodological errors increase, and, as a result, professional responsibility decreases. This situation indicates the need for new approaches in the system of teacher training.

Currently, foreign experience in the development of pedagogical competencies shows that a teacher should act not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a person who manages, directs, and psychologically supports the development of students. Professional responsibility is formed precisely in this process. A responsive, reflexive, creative, and innovative teacher can be responsible for the results of his or her activities.

The introduction substantiates the content of pedagogical competence, the stages of its formation, and its impact on professional responsibility. Conducting in-depth analysis and research on this topic is necessary to improve the quality of education and further improve pedagogical practice.

There are various approaches in the scientific literature on pedagogical competence, and most authors interpret competence as a set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and personal qualities of a teacher. The works of Uzbek scientists - R. Ishmuhammedov, N. Kayumov, R. Tolipov, M. Ochilov - extensively cover the content of pedagogical competence, its components and methods of application in the educational process. In particular, Tolipov shows pedagogical competence as a person who is able to use innovative approaches in the educational process, is technologically equipped, and communicatively mature.

In foreign studies, the level of professional responsibility of a teacher is assessed based on the competency model. The works of D. MacClelland, J. Raven, H. Hutmacher link the professional competence of a teacher with psychological preparation, motivation and professional values. The State Educational Standards (STS) adopted in Uzbekistan also require technological, methodological, innovative, communicative and social competencies from a teacher.

The study of the literature shows that the development of pedagogical competencies is inextricably linked with the professional responsibility of the teacher. For example, if a teacher has methodological competence, he will correctly organize the lesson plan, technology, assessment criteria and will approach the process responsibly. Communicative competence, on the other hand, creates a positive educational environment through healthy communication with students and psychological support. Reflective competence ensures that the teacher evaluates and improves his own activities.

The analysis of the literature also shows that there are factors that hinder the development of pedagogical competencies: lack of methodological resources, low efficiency of the professional development system, slowness of the practice-oriented educational process, insufficient motivation and psychological preparation of teachers. These factors lead to a decrease in professional responsibility. The study was aimed at studying the process of developing pedagogical competencies and forming professional responsibility through them, using practical and theoretical methods. Initially, a diagnostic questionnaire was conducted among a group of teachers of secondary schools and higher education institutions to assess the level of competencies. According to the results of the questionnaire, 43% of teachers had a high level of methodological competence, while communicative and innovative competencies were around 32–35%. This indicated that teachers need to develop some types of competencies.

During the study, the level of professional responsibility of teachers was also studied separately. Indicators were developed based on the criteria of lesson preparation, assessment system, educational approach, communication with students, and analysis of their own activities. According to the results, it was noted that teachers with a high level of competencies also have high professional responsibility.

The study identified the following as the most effective methods for developing pedagogical competencies:

- use of interactive methods;
- mentoring, teacher-student system;
- reflexive practice;
- advanced training based on practical exercises;
- self-assessment monitoring;
- directions for creating methodological developments based on digital technologies.

Also, pilot classes were organized, during which special trainings were conducted to improve pedagogical competencies. The results of the training showed that after two months of practical exercises, the communicative competence of teachers increased by 18%, methodological competence by 22%, and reflexive competence by 27%.

The results of the study confirmed that pedagogical competencies play a decisive role in the formation of a teacher's professional responsibility. Proper design of the lesson process, ensuring the active participation of students, accurate application of assessment criteria and fulfillment of educational tasks rely on the developed level of competencies. The study showed that teachers with high methodological, communicative and reflexive competencies have a 30–40% higher level of professional responsibility.

Exchange of experience between teachers through the mentoring system increases professional responsibility, and a reflexive approach enhances the critical analysis of the teacher's own activities. Interactive methods, training sessions and digital technologies have emerged as the most effective means of developing competence.

Conclusion

The development of pedagogical competencies is one of the main factors in the formation of professional responsibility in teachers. The results of the study show that teachers with developed competencies take a responsible approach to their activities, effectively organize the educational process, and directly affect the quality of education. The formation of professional responsibility is primarily associated with the methodological, communicative, innovative, and reflexive competencies of the teacher, and their systematic development is an integral task of the education system.

In the development of pedagogical competencies, reflexive practice, the teacher-student system, interactive methods, advanced training courses, and the introduction of digital technologies into the teaching process are recommended as the most effective tools. Based on this article, it was concluded that it is necessary to apply a broader competency-based approach in the process of training teachers, strengthen professional responsibility, and improve the system for monitoring teacher activity.

References:

1. Ishmuhammedov R. Innovative pedagogical technologies. — Tashkent, 2020.
2. Tolipov R., Kayumov N. Fundamentals of pedagogical competence. — Tashkent: Fan, 2018.
3. Ochilov M. Competency-based approach to the educational process. — Samarkand, 2021.
4. Yuldosheva N. Pedagogical skills and competence. — Tashkent, 2019.
5. Abdukodirov A. Educational technologies. — Tashkent, 2020.
6. Karimova D. Fundamentals of pedagogical psychology. — Tashkent, 2018.
7. Yakubov Kh. Pedagogical monitoring and evaluation. — Fergana, 2022.